

hydrochloride (2.22 g, 0.02 mol) and ethanolic solution of *p*-vanillin (3.04 g, 0.02 mol) were mixed in the presence in sodium acetate (2.72 g, 0.02 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously for an hour. On cooling white coloured compound was precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Yield (65%), m.p. 190 °C (Found : C, 51.9; H, 5.0; N, 20.3. Calcd. for C₉H₁₁N₃O₃ (for molecular mass 209) : C, 51.7; H, 5.3; N, 20.0%).

Synthesis of complexes : Hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding metal salts (0.01 mol) were mixed with hot ethanolic solution of the respective ligands (0.01 mol) and refluxed for 3–4 h at 70–80 °C. On cooling the coloured complex separated out. It was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Physical measurements : The C, H and N were analyzed on Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the Elico (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as a calibrant. Electronic impact mass spectra were recorded on Jeol, JMS-DX-303 mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra were recorded as polycrystalline samples at room tem-

perature on E₄-EPR spectrometer using DPPH as the *g*-marker. The voltammograms were recorded on an X-Y Houston-Ommigraphic recorder.

Results and discussion

On the basis of elemental analysis, the complexes were found assigned the composition shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements in DMSO correspond to 1 : 1 electrolytic nature for Cr^{III} complexes and non-electrolytes nature for the Mn^{II} complexes⁴. Thus the complexes may be formulated as [Cr(L)₂X₂]X and [Mn(L)₂X₂] [L = L¹ and L² and X = Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻].

The electronic impact mass spectrum of the ligand (L¹) shows a molecular ion (M⁺) peak at *m/z* 226 amu corresponding to species [C₉H₁₁N₃O₂S]⁻, confirms the proposed formula (Fig. 2). It also shows series of peaks at 16, 60, 89, 102, 123, 136, 165 and 208 amu corresponding to various fragments. The electronic impact mass spectrum of the ligand (L²) shows a molecular ion (M⁺) peak at *m/z* 210 amu corresponding to species [C₉H₁₁N₃O₃]⁻, confirms the proposed formula (Fig. 3). It also shows series of peaks at 16, 44, 60, 73, 90, 110, 136, 166 and 182 amu corresponding to various fragments. The intensities of these peaks give the idea of the stabilities of the fragments.

In the mass spectrum of [Cr(L¹)₂Cl₂]Cl complex mo-

Table 1. Molar conductance and elemental analysis data of the complexes

Complex	Molecular weight	Molar conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
						Found (Calcd.)			
						M	C	H	N
[Cr(L ¹) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	609	87	Green	291	82	8.7	35.7	3.8	13.6
CrC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₃						(8.5)	(35.5)	(3.6)	(13.8)
[Cr(L ¹) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	688	90	Light green	269	70	7.5	31.5	3.3	18.1
CrC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₉ O ₁₃ S ₂						(7.6)	(31.4)	(3.2)	(18.3)
[Mn(L ¹) ₂ Cl ₂]	576	12	White	285	65	9.7	37.7	3.6	14.3
MnC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂						(9.5)	(37.5)	(3.8)	(14.6)
[Mn(L ¹) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	629	16	White	270	62	8.10	34.1	3.2	17.2
MnC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₁₀ S ₂						(8.8)	(34.3)	(3.5)	(17.8)
[Cr(L ²) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	577	75	Shiny green	279	75	9.2	37.3	3.10	14.3
CrC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₃						(9.0)	(37.4)	(3.8)	(14.6)
[Cr(L ²) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	656	82	Dark green	298	68	7.8	32.7	3.1	19.3
CrC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₉ O ₁₅						(7.9)	(32.9)	(3.4)	(19.2)
[Mn(L ²) ₂ Cl ₂]	544	15	Light brown	265	60	10.5	39.2	4.2	15.7
MnC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂						(10.1)	(39.7)	(4.0)	(15.5)
[Mn(L ²) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	597	18	Brown	278	57	9.3	36.4	3.5	18.5
MnC ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₁₀						(9.2)	(36.2)	(3.7)	(18.8)

Fig. 2. Electronic impact mass spectrum of the ligand (L^1).

Fig. 3. Electronic impact mass spectrum of the ligand (L^2).

lecular ion (M^+) peak is observed at m/z 610 amu corresponding to species $[Cr(L^1)_2Cl_2]Cl^-$, confirms the proposed formula (Fig. 4). It also shows series of peaks at 16, 36, 60, 75, 102, 144, 212, 279, 330, 397, 465, 507, 534, 549 and 593 amu corresponding to various fragments. Mass spectrum of complex $[Mn(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]$ shows molecular ion (M^+) peak at m/z 516 amu corresponding to species $[Mn(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]^-$, confirms the proposed for-

Fig. 4. Electronic impact mass spectrum of the complex $[Cr(L^1)_2Cl_2]Cl$.

Fig. 5. Electronic impact mass spectrum of the complex $[Mn(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]$.

mula. Its also shows series of peaks at 44, 59, 86, 146, 204, 270, 327, 395, 457, 511, 538, 553 and 581 amu (Fig. 5). The intensities of these peaks give the idea of the stabilities of the fragments.

The 1H NMR spectra of the ligands show the resonance for the methoxy protons appeared as a singlet at δ 3.61 ppm in ligands and in complexes no significant change was observed. Significant azomethane proton signal, due to $HC=N$ was observed at δ 8.05–9.05 ppm region as a multiplet in ligands and in complexes it has shown a change as a downfield shift and occurred at δ 8.22–9.22 ppm, indicating involvement of nitrogen in coordination. The proton of N–H group at δ 10.5–11.1 ppm remains the same in the ligands and in the complexes which indicates that deprotonation do not occur.

Infrared spectra of the ligands show bands in the region 1580 and 1560 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric $\nu(C=N)$ vibrations. A strong band in the region ~ 782 cm^{-1} in thiosemicarbazone and ~ 1692 cm^{-1} in semicarbazone are due to $\nu(C=S)$ and $\nu(C=O)$ groups, respectively. On complex formation, the position of these bands is shifted toward lower side as compared the metal free ligand. This indicates that the coordination takes place through the nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen atom of the (C=N), (C=S) and (C=O) groups. Thus, it has been concluded that the semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones act as bidentate chelating agent.

The infrared spectra of the nitrate complexes of Cr^{III} display three medium intensity bands in the region at 1420–1438 (ν_2), 1304–1320 (ν_1) and 998–1021 (ν_2) cm^{-1} respectively. The separation between ν_2 and ν_1 is found 116–118 cm^{-1} which indicates the unidentate⁵ nature of nitrate group. A broad band at ~ 1387 –1392 cm^{-1} corres-

ponding to uncoordinated nitrate. Whereas nitrate complexes of Mn^{II} display three (N-O) stretching bands in the range 1430–1445 (ν_3), 1312–1326 (ν_1) and 1008–1018 (ν_2) cm^{-1} , suggests that both the nitrate groups are coordinated to the central metal ion⁶.

Chromium(III) complexes : The magnetic moment recorded at room temperature lies in the range 3.62–3.80 B.M., corresponding to three unpaired electrons (Table 2). Electronic spectra of Cr^{III} complexes in DMSO solution, display four weak intensity absorption bands (Table 2) in the 18450–18587 ($\epsilon = 32$ –34 $L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$), 22321–22500 ($\epsilon = 40$ –45 $L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$) and 24500–25316 ($\epsilon = 52$ –57 $L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$) range. These bands may be assigned to the transitions corresponding to the spin allowed transitions ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$. It is difficult to make the assignments for the third band and it may be considered as a charge transfer band. EPR spectra were recorded as a polycrystalline sample at room temperature possess an isotropic single broad line spectra. The g values lies in the range 1.98–2.09 and are given in Table 3.

Manganese(II) complexes : The magnetic moment recorded at room temperature lies in the 5.90–5.97 B.M. range, corresponding to five unpaired electrons. Electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complexes exhibit four weak inten-

sity absorption bands in the range 17650–18750 ($\epsilon = 32$ –35 $L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$), 21982–23085 ($\epsilon = 40$ –42 $L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$), 26315–27778 ($\epsilon = 59$ –61 $L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$) and 35936–38170 ($\epsilon = 124$ –127 $L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$). These bands may be assigned to the transitions : ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}({}^4G)$ ($10B + 5C$), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4D)$ ($17B + 5C$) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4P)$ ($7B + 7C$) respectively. The position of these bands suggest an octahedral geometry around the Mn^{II} ion⁷. The EPR spectra of the complexes have been recorded as polycrystalline sample and given in Table 3. The polycrystalline samples gives one broad

Fig. 6. EPR spectrum of $[Mn(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]$ complex.

Table 2. Magnetic moment and electronic spectral data of the complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})	ϵ ($L\ mol^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$)
$[Cr(L^1)_2Cl_2]Cl$	3.68	18450, 22271, 25316	34, 41, 63
$[Cr(L^1)_2(NO_3)_2]NO_3$	3.62	18500, 22500, 25715	35, 44, 63
$[Mn(L^1)_2Cl_2]$	5.92	18312, 22778, 27438, 38170	32, 45, 64, 125
$[Mn(L^1)_2(NO_3)_2]$	5.95	17650, 21982, 26315, 36370	29, 44, 62, 122
$[Cr(L^2)_2Cl_2]Cl$	3.75	18587, 22321, 24937	35, 42, 61
$[Cr(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]NO_3$	3.80	18348, 22471, 24500	32, 44, 59
$[Mn(L^2)_2Cl_2]$	5.97	18750, 23085, 27785, 37364	34, 47, 65, 125
$[Mn(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]$	5.90	17912, 22700, 27100, 35936	30, 45, 65, 121

Table 3. Ligand field parameters and g values of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	C (cm^{-1})	β	LFSE ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	g	F_4	F_2	h_x
$[Cr(L^1)_2Cl_2]Cl$	1845	341	-	0.37	265	1.98	-	-	-
$[Cr(L^1)_2(NO_3)_2]NO_3$	1850	358	-	0.39	265	2.01	-	-	-
$[Mn(L^1)_2Cl_2]$	1831	666	3223	0.84	-	1.97	92	-	2.29
$[Mn(L^1)_2(NO_3)_2]$	1765	619	3158	0.79	-	2.07	90	-	3.00
$[Cr(L^2)_2Cl_2]Cl$	1858	335	-	0.36	266	2.05	-	-	-
$[Cr(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]NO_3$	1834	371	-	0.40	263	2.09	-	-	-
$[Mn(L^1)_2Cl_2]$	1875	670	3277	0.85	-	1.99	94	-	2.14
$[Mn(L^2)_2(NO_3)_2]$	1791	629	3282	0.80	-	2.02	94	-	2.86

isotropic (Fig. 6) signal centered approximately at around the free electron g value (2.0023).

Ligand field parameters : Various ligand field parameters were calculated for the complexes and are listed in Table 3. The Nephelauxetic parameter β is obtained by using the relation : $\beta = B(\text{complex})/B(\text{free ion})$, where $B(\text{Free ion})$ for Cr^{III} is 918 and for Mn^{II} is 786 cm^{-1} . The values of β lie in the range 0.36-0.84 indicate appreciable covalent character in the complexes. In the Mn^{II} the values B and C were calculated from the second and third transitions because these transitions are free from the crystal field splitting and depend on B and C parameters⁸.

Fig. 7. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ in MeCN.

Electrochemical studies : Redox properties of the manganese(II) complexes were studied by cyclic voltammetry (CV) using a platinum working electrode. Cyclic voltammogram is shown in Fig. 7. A couple appears at 0.80–1.1 V versus SCE is referred to $\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ redox process⁹. The quasireversibility of the process is examined from peak-to-peak separation, $\Delta E_p > 100 \text{ mV}$. One electron nature of the redox process has been confirmed by DPV studies. Ligand reductions are irreversible in nature and the E_{pc} values are comparable with free ligand values. The electrochemical properties of chromium(III) complexes were studied by cyclic voltammetry in acetonitrile solvent. The reduction wave was observed at -490 to -560 mV versus $\text{Ag}/\text{Ag}^+/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$, respectively. The oxidation wave of complexes were observed at -40 to 92 mV . Also, the separation between the redox waves for oxidation and reduction processes was surprisingly 300 – 420 mV . All the complexes showed additional irreversible one-electron reduction

$M = \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ and Mn^{II} , $X = \text{Cl}^-$ and NO_3^- ,
 $n = 1$ for Cr^{III} and $n = 0$ for Mn^{II}

Fig. 8. Suggested structure of the complexes.

waves near -1300 mV . The process could be attributed to the reduction of the Cr^{III} to Cr^{II} ion¹⁰.

On the basis of above spectral studies an octahedral geometry (Fig. 8) may be suggested for the complexes.

Antifungal screening :

The preliminary fungitoxicity screening of the compounds were performed against the phytopathogenic fungi *Rhizoctonia bataticola*, *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium odum* were performed *in vitro* by the Food poison technique¹¹. Stock solutions of compounds were prepared by dissolving the compounds in DMSO. Ketoconazol used as commercial fungicide and DMSO served as control. Potato dextrose agar medium was prepared by using potato, dextrose, agar-agar and distilled water. The appropriate quantity of the compounds in DMSO were directly mixed to the potato agar dextrose (PDA) medium in different concentrations. When the medium in the plates was solidified, a mycelial discs of 0.5 cm in diameter cut from the periphery of the 7 days old culture and it was aseptically inoculated upside down in the centre of the petriplates. These treated Petri dishes were incubated at $26 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until fungal growth in the control petriplates was almost complete.

The inhibition of fungal growths expressed in percentage terms was determined on the growth in test plates compared to the respective control plates as given inhibition%.

Graph. 1. Antifungal activities.

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = 100(C - T)/C,$$

(where C , diameter of the fungal growth on the control; T , diameter of the fungal growth on the test plate). The activities of the compounds have been compared with the activity of standard fungicide Ketoconazol. The observed results revealed an enhancement of the antifungal activity of ligands in the form of their metal complexes which can be well explained in the light of chelation theory¹² (Graph 1).

References

- I. Kizilcikh, B. Ulkuseven, Y. Oasdemir and B. Akkurt, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2004, **34**, 653.
- N. K. Singh, S. B. Singh, A. Shrivastava and S. M. Singh, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 2001, **113**, 257.
- E. M. Jouad, G. Larcher, M. Allain, A. Riou, G. M. Bouet, M. A. Khan and X. D. Thanh, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2001, **86**, 565; D. C. Quenelle, K. A. Keith and E. R. Kern, *Antiviral Research*, 2006, **71**, 24; Z. Afrasiabi, E. Sinn, J. Chen, Y. Ma, A. L. Rheingold, L. N. Zakharov, N. Rath and S. Pandey, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **357**, 271; N. Bharti, F. Athar, M. R. Maurya and Amir Azam, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 4679; N. C. Kasuga, K. Sekino, M. Ishikawa, A. Honda, M. Yokoyama, S. Nakano, N. Shimada, C. Koumo and K. Nomiya, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2003, **96**, 298; M. C. Rodríguez-Argüelles, E. C. López-Silva, J. Sanmartín, A. Bacchi, C. Pelizzi and F. Zani, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **35**, 2543; C. Rigol, C. Olea-Azar, F. Mendizábal, L. Otero, D. Gambino, M. González and H. Cerecetto, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2005, **61**, 2933; S. Prasad and R. K. Agarwal, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 143; N. K. Singh and A. Srivastava, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2000, **25**, 133.
- S. Chandra and A. Kumar, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **10**, 491; W. G. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81; A. Garg and J. P. Tandon, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 212; K. K. Aravindaksan and K. Muraleedharan, *React. Solids*, 1990, **8**, 91.
- S. Chandra and R. Kumar, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2007, **66**, 74.
- C. R. K. Rao and P. S. Zacharias, *Polyhedron*, 1977, **12**, 2775; S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 2767, 3079; S. Chandra and U. Kumar, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **8**, 77; S. Chandra, U. Kumar and H. S. Verma, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **7**, 337; S. Chandra and Sangeetika, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 147.
- A. B. P. Lever, "Crystal Field Spectra, Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, 249; S. Chandra and A. Kumar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 325; *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **10**, 485; J. R. Perumareddi, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 73.
- C. Preti and G. Tosi, *J. Aust. Chem.*, 1976, **20**, 243; L. E. Orgel, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2002, **27**, 329; V. V. Pavlishchuk, S. P. Kolotilov, A. W. Addison, R. J. Butche and E. Sinn, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 335; S. Chandra and K. Gupta, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 329; S. Chandra, K. Gupta and S. Sharma, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 1205; S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 833.
- T. Mathur, U. S. Ray, J.-C. Liou, J.-S. Wu, T.-H. Lu and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 739.
- A. S. Attita, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 2550.
- I. M. Vincent, *Nature*, 1927, 159; M. Nagar, S. Rawat, R. Sharma, H. Sharma and M. Agarwal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 341.
- W. H. R. Shaw, *Nature*, 1961, **192**, 754.